

Study on technology acceptance, familiarity and anshin-kan

This questionnaire is intended to survey your opinions regarding risk acceptance and perceived safety.

It is expected to take approximately 10 minutes to complete.

Please note that survey responses will be processed statistically and will not be made public as information that can identify specific individuals.

We apologize for bothering you during your busy schedule, but we would appreciate your cooperation.

If you have any questions, please contact us at the address listed below.

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In order to collect accurate data, please be sure to observe the following precautions:

- If you normally wear glasses or contact lenses, please wear them before answering the survey.
- Answer the survey alone, without consulting with anyone.
- Do not eat or drink while answering the survey.
- Answer the survey in a quiet room with music and television turned off.
- Answer the survey in a well-lit room.
- Make the screen bright enough so that it is not dazzling.
- Display only this survey content on the screen.
- Keep your face about 60cm away from the screen.

Do not look up or check information online or in other reference materials while answering the survey. If you do not understand some words or concepts, it will not affect your results.

Consent Form

When you participate in the survey, we will not ask you for personal information such as your name. When you begin the survey, you will have agreed to participate in the research, and there will be no disadvantage if you discontinue the survey midway. However, because the survey is anonymous, responses once submitted cannot be retracted later. If you understand the above points and would like to cooperate with this survey, please select "I Agree" below and press the "Next" button to begin the survey.

Agree

Disagree

(Next)

Risk Assessment

How confident do you feel about the following technologies? Please choose the answer that best describes your feelings from the options below (completely disagree means you feel very uneasy and completely agree means you feel very confident).

Do you feel safe with the following science and technology?

	Totally Disagree	Disagree	I am not sure	Agree	Totally agree
Self-driving private cars	1	2	3	4	5
Automated delivery robots	1	2	3	4	5
Self-driving trains	1	2	3	4	5
Electric Vehicles (EV)	1	2	3	4	5
Reception robots	1	2	3	4	5
Security Robot	1	2	3	4	5
Pet Robot	1	2	3	4	5
Cleaning Robot	1	2	3	4	5
AI (Artificial Intelligence)	1	2	3	4	5
Virtual Assistants	1	2	3	4	5
Virtual reality goggles	1	2	3	4	5
Wearables (smart watches, smart rings, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5
Webcams	1	2	3	4	5
5G	1	2	3	4	5
Microwave ovens	1	2	3	4	5
Drones	1	2	3	4	5
Corona Vaccine	1	2	3	4	5
Cancer Vaccine	1	2	3	4	5
HIV Vaccine	1	2	3	4	5
Nuclear power	1	2	3	4	5
Nuclear fusion	1	2	3	4	5
Solar power	1	2	3	4	5
Hydrogen Engine	1	2	3	4	5
Dams	1	2	3	4	5
Biomass fuels	1	2	3	4	5
Gene therapy	1	2	3	4	5
Cloning technology	1	2	3	4	5

Artificial cells	1	2	3	4	5
Pesticides	1	2	3	4	5
Food additives	1	2	3	4	5
Genetically Modified Crops	1	2	3	4	5
Generic drugs	1	2	3	4	5
Functional Foods	1	2	3	4	5
Plant factories	1	2	3	4	5
Proton therapy	1	2	3	4	5
Insect Food	1	2	3	4	5
Cultured Meat	1	2	3	4	5
Artificial sweeteners	1	2	3	4	5
Chemical fertilizers	1	2	3	4	5
Urban beekeeping	1	2	3	4	5
Smartphones	1	2	3	4	5
Social Media	1	2	3	4	5
Cyber Terrorism	1	2	3	4	5
E-commerce	1	2	3	4	5
Facial recognition systems (biometric security systems)	1	2	3	4	5
X-rays	1	2	3	4	5
MRI (magnetic resonance imaging)	1	2	3	4	5
Blood transfusion	1	2	3	4	5
Facial transplantation	1	2	3	4	5
Electronic voting	1	2	3	4	5

If you want to delete data, select the topmost or middle option. If you do not want to delete data, select the option at the bottom.

- Delete data.
- Delete data.
- Do not delete data.

Familiarity

How familiar do you feel with the following technologies? Please choose the answer from the options below that most closely matches your thoughts. (Not familiar with at all means that you have never heard of the technology you are evaluating or feel that you do not know it at all; Knowing a little means that you have heard of it or do not know it deeply but feel that you know a little about it; Knowing a lot means that you can explain it and have studied it.)

How familiar do you feel you are with the following science and technology?

	I don' t know about it	I know a little about it	I know a lot about it
Self-driving private cars	1	2	3
Automated delivery robots	1	2	3
Self-driving trains	1	2	3
Electric Vehicles (EV)	1	2	3
Reception robots	1	2	3
Security Robot	1	2	3
Pet Robot	1	2	3
Cleaning Robot	1	2	3
AI (Artificial Intelligence)	1	2	3
Virtual Assistants	1	2	3
Virtual reality goggles	1	2	3
Wearables (smart watches, smart rings, etc.)	1	2	3
Webcams	1	2	3
5G	1	2	3
Microwave ovens	1	2	3
Drones	1	2	3
Corona Vaccine	1	2	3
Cancer Vaccine	1	2	3
HIV Vaccine	1	2	3
Nuclear power	1	2	3
Nuclear fusion	1	2	3
Solar power	1	2	3
Hydrogen Engine	1	2	3
Dams	1	2	3
Biomass fuels	1	2	3
Gene therapy	1	2	3

Cloning technology	1	2	3
Artificial cells	1	2	3
Food additives	1	2	3
Genetically Modified Crops	1	2	3
Pesticides	1	2	3
Generic drugs	1	2	3
Functional Foods	1	2	3
Plant factories	1	2	3
Proton therapy	1	2	3
Insect Food	1	2	3
Cultured Meat	1	2	3
Artificial sweeteners	1	2	3
Chemical fertilizers	1	2	3
Urban beekeeping	1	2	3
Smartphones	1	2	3
Social Media	1	2	3
Cyber Terrorism	1	2	3
E-commerce	1	2	3
Facial recognition systems (biometric security systems)	1	2	3
X-rays	1	2	3
MRI (magnetic resonance imaging)	1	2	3
Blood transfusion	1	2	3
Facial transplantation	1	2	3
Electronic voting	1	2	3

2+2=?

- 4
- 5
- 1

Risk Acceptance

To what extent are you able to accept the following technologies? Please choose the answer that at most closely matches your opinion from the options below ("Unacceptable" means that you feel it is completely unacceptable, while "Acceptable" means that you feel that you can accept it even if there are risks).

To what extent are you willing to accept the following science and technology?

	Cannot accept	Somewhat not acceptable	I don't know	Somewhat acceptable	Acceptable
Self-driving private cars	1	2	3	4	5
Automated delivery robots	1	2	3	4	5
Self-driving trains	1	2	3	4	5
Electric Vehicles (EV)	1	2	3	4	5
Reception robots	1	2	3	4	5
Security Robot	1	2	3	4	5
Pet Robot	1	2	3	4	5
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Drones	1	2	3	4	5
Corona Vaccine	1	2	3	4	5
Cancer Vaccine	1	2	3	4	5
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Nuclear fusion	1	2	3	4	5
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Dams	1	2	3	4	5
Biomass fuels	1	2	3	4	5
Gene therapy	1	2	3	4	5

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Blood transfusion	1	2	3	4	5
Facial transplantation	1	2	3	4	5
Electronic voting	1	2	3	4	5

Demographic Information

Age :

Gender :

<input type="radio"/>	Female
<input type="radio"/>	Male
<input type="radio"/>	Prefer not to answer

Nationality :

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Academic Background:

<input type="radio"/>	Highschool graduate
<input type="radio"/>	Bachelor' s degree
<input type="radio"/>	Vocational School degree
<input type="radio"/>	Master' s degree
<input type="radio"/>	Doctoral degree or higher
<input type="radio"/>	Other:

Specialization Field :

What was your specialization when you studied at university or college? If no specialization, please state 'no specialization' .

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If you feel insecure about any other technology, please describe it in the space below.

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(End)